

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

STUDY TO DETERMINE THE PATTERN OF RENAL DISEASES AMONG CHILDREN

¹Dr Safia Akhtar, ²Dr Tayyaba Sohail, ³Dr Muhammad Ali

¹Azad Jammu and Kashmir Medical College

²Islamic International Medical College

³Azad Jammu and Kashmir Medical College

Article Received: October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020

Abstract:

Introduction: The characteristics of kidney disease in children differ from congenital kidney and urinary tract defects (CAKUT), such as obstructive uropathies, to acquired glomerulonephritis, urolithiasis and urinary tract infections (UTI).

Aims: To determine the pattern of renal diseases in children in our setup.

Methods: Children 1 month to 18 years of age with kidney disease who reported to Pediatric Nephrology department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi for one-year duration from November 2019 to November 2020.

Results: Out of 602 patients, 393 were male and 207 were female. Mean + SD age was 7.2 + 4.21 years. Edema (56%), anemia (38%), painful urination (37%), fever (36%) and burning micturition (34%) were common symptoms. The most common diseases were nephrotic syndrome (NS 49%), chronic kidney disease (CKD 29%) and urolithiasis (4%). Other diseases include congenital obstructive uropathy (3.5%), acute kidney injury (AKI 3%), acute glomerulonephritis (AGN 2%), hypoplastic dysplastic kidney disease (2%), UTIs, neurogenic bladder, and vesicoureteral reflex (VUR). In 321 cases with GN, 290 had NS, 13 had acute GN, 8 had secondary GN, and 3 had congenital NS. Among NS, 268 (90.52%) was presumably Minimal Change Disease (MCD), while 30 had steroid resistance, 14 had focal segmental glomerulosclerosis, 6 membranoproliferative GN, 5 MCD; 2 each had membranous GN and IgM nephropathy. In 173 patients with CKD, the most common causes were renal hypoplasia and dysplasia (39.3%), urinary stones (25.6%), and posterior urethral valves (PUV19%). Other causes were juvenile nephronophthisis (10.4%), VUR (8.6%), neurogenic bladder (7.5%), and cystic kidney disease (5.2%). Among 186 people with CAKUT, renal hypoplasia and dysplasia were found in 43%, PUV in 29%, and VUR in 12.9%.

Conclusion: The current spectrum of kidney disease has shown that the most common kidney diseases are PNS, CKD and urinary stones.

Key words: primary nephrotic syndrome, chronic kidney disease, congenital defects of the kidneys and urinary tract, urolithiasis, acute kidney injury

Corresponding author:

Dr. Safia Akhtar,

Azad Jammu and Kashmir Medical College

QR code

Please cite this article in press Safia Akhtar et al., *Study To Determine The Pattern Of Renal Diseases Among Children.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

The pattern of kidney disease in children varies geographically due to environmental, racial, genetic and cultural differences. Children develop kidney disease early in life, and the spectrum varies from congenital kidney and urinary tract disorders (CAKUT) such as obstructive uropathies, hypoplasia, and tubular disorders such as Fanconi syndrome, to acquired urinary tract disorders such as primary and secondary glomerulonephritis, urolithiasis and recurrent UTIs. Congenital kidney disorders are the most commonly reported kidney disease in developed countries due to early-stage diagnosis, while in developing countries, acquired kidney disorders such as chronic GN, tartar diseases and infectious diseases are more common. Even children with congenital kidney disease with complications of advanced chronic kidney disease (CKD) and approximately 12% of pediatric nephrology patients in a neighboring country had moderate to severe CKD with a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) <50 ml / min per 1.73 m² a 25% of them already had end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). A similar frequency (11%) was recorded in Iran, where 50% had advanced ESKD. Common diagnoses reported in the Iranian study were acute nephritis (23%), UTI (19.1%), nephrotic syndrome (18.6%), CKD (14.9%), urological problems (7.5%), acute kidney damage (7.3%), disorders (3.5%) and hypertension (2.9%). Little information exists about the epidemiology of the early stages of CKD, which are potentially more susceptible to therapeutic interventions to alter the course of the disease and avoid ESKD. Knowing the spectrum of urinary tract disorders and their clinical symptoms will help target key groups of patients at risk by assessing the extent of the problem that can be adequately treated to avoid the development of progressive CKD requiring long-term renal replacement therapy, which is expensive in developing countries such as Pakistan. In Pakistan, data on kidney disease in children is scarce due to the lack of a national registry and it is mainly based on patients referred to medical centers. In our previous retrospective data, the most common renal dysfunction was nephrotic syndrome (43%), followed by congenital kidney disease (17.36%), urolithiasis (14%), and CKD (10.37%). Pediatric nephrology is relatively new particular in Pakistan with just a few well-developed centers. The options for renal replacement therapy for children and adolescents with CKD are limited. An Automated Peritoneal Dialysis program will remain a dream for young infants, although few centers are well equipped with hemodialysis facilities for older children and

adolescents. An audit of kidney disease in children can provide data that can help planners to prevent disease in the future. Therefore, we planned a prospective study of patterns of kidney disease in children.

METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted on children 1 month to 18 years of age with kidney disease who reported to Pediatric Nephrology department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi for one-year duration from November 2019 to November 2020. All children with various urinary tract diseases (operative definitions) were enrolled in the study after obtaining consent parents. In all cases, a detailed clinical evaluation was performed including a history and appropriate physical examination, followed by laboratory tests including a complete blood picture, urinalysis, serum creatinine, urea, electrolytes, and ultrasound of the kidneys, ureters and bladder (USKUB) in all cases. In patients with CKD, serum levels of calcium, phosphorus and alkaline phosphatase were measured. In patients with primary and secondary GN, serum proteins, albumin, cholesterol and the urine protein to creatinine ratio were tested. Urine culture and sensitivity (CS), voiding cysto-ureterogram (MCUG), and kidney DMSA testing were performed for UTI, VUR, PUV, and neurogenic bladder. Intravenous pyelography (IVP) was performed in children with urolithiasis or unilateral obstruction of the upper urinary tract or with a duplex system, ectopic kidneys or horseshoe. All of these tests, including hematology, biochemistry, microbiology, and radio imaging, were performed according to standard

Statistical analysis: Data including age, gender, weight and height, place of residence (village / town), clinical results and laboratory tests were collected on a special proforma and analyzed using the Social Sciences Statistical Package (SPSS) version 19. The results were expressed as the mean and standard deviation (SD) for quantitative variables such as age, serum creatinine, while the frequency and percentages were used for qualitative variables such as gender, symptoms, etc.

RESULTS:

Out of 602 examined patients, 393 were men (65.5%) and 207 women (34.5%). The mean age + SD of the patients was 7.2 + 4.21 years, and the most common age group was 5-10 years (239, 39.70%), followed by 1-5 years (192, 31.89%). Most cases (n = 282; 46.8%) were referred by a family doctor, 192 (31.9%) from health care institutions, and 128 (21.26%) - by themselves. The reason for referral

was procedure 444, diagnosis 137, surgery 11 and dialysis 10. Out of 334 (55.48%) admissions to the nephrology ward, 200 (59.88%) were admitted to OPD, 88 (26.34%) to the emergency ward and 46 (13.77%) were transferred from other entities. The reasons for admission were: procedure (n = 195, 58.38%), diagnosis (n = 55, 16.76%), kidney biopsy

(n = 38, 11.33%), surgery (n = 25, 7.48) and dialysis (n = 20.5.98%). In 36 (5.98%) cases, kidney disease was positive, and the most common diseases were NS 12 and urolithiasis 6. Overall, clinical symptoms of children with kidney diseases are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Pattern of clinical presentation (n=602)

Symptoms and signs	No	Percentage
Edema	338	56.1
Anemia	228	36.9
Dysuria	221	36.7
Fever	215	35.7
Burning micturition	203	33.7
Vomiting	178	29.6
Retention of Urine	103	17.1
Oligo-anuria	78	13
Palpable urinary bladder	73	12.1
CNS manifestations	66	11.0
Walking difficulty	57	9.5
Signs of mineral bone disease	52	8.6
Metabolic acidosis	43	7.10
Hematuria	41	6.8
Joint/Bone pain	33	5.5
Surgical Scar	45	7.5
Skin rashes	25	4.2
Tender abdomen	12	2.0
Palpable kidneys	14	2.3

The most common was edema (56%), followed by anemia (38%), painful urination (36.71%), fever (35.71%) and burning micturition (33.7%). Other important symptoms were vomiting (29.6%), urinary retention (17.1%), oliguria (13%), and palpable bladder contact (12.1%). The comparative pattern of kidney disease in this study versus the Iranian study is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Comparative pattern of pediatric kidney diseases in our study with Iranian study

Type of renal disease	Current study (N=602) N (%)	Study from Iran ⁵ (N=1358) N(%)
Nephrotic Syndrome	297(49.3)	232(18.6)
Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)	173(28.7)	202(14.9)
Urinary Stone disease	24(4)	32(2.4)
Congenital Obstructive Uropathies	21(3.5)	62(4.5)
Acute Renal Failure (ARF)	17(2.8)	99(7.3)
Acute Glomerulonephritis (AGN)	13(2.2)	147(10.8)
Hypoplastic kidneys	12(2)	----
Urinary Tract Infection (UTI)	8(1.3)	260(19.1)
Secondary		
Glomerulonephritis (SGN)	8(1.3)	85(6.25)
Neurogenic Bladder (NGB)	7(1.2)	17(1.2)
Primary Vesico - Ureteral Reflux (VUR)	5(0.8)	19(1.4)
Congenital Nephrotic Syndrome	3(0.5)	21(1.5)

Others	18(2.9)	---
--------	---------	-----

Primary NS, CKD, and urolithiasis were the most common kidney diseases in this study. Other important diseases are congenital obstructive uropathy, AKI and hypoplastic-dysplastic kidney disease 12. Table 3 shows the comparative etiology of CKD in the present study versus the Lahore study.

TABLE 3: Etiology of chronic kidney diseases in present study compared with a study from Lahore

Etiology	Present study N=173		Study from Lahore ¹³ N=42	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Hypoplasia-dysplasia	68	39.30	-	-
Urinary stone disease	47	25.68	5	12
Posterior urethral valves	33	19.07	11	26
Juvenile Nephronophthiasis	18	10.40	2	4.7
Vesicoureteral Reflux	15	8.67	4	9.5
Neurogenic Bladder	13	7.51	2	4.7
Cystic renal diseases	9	5.20	2	4.7
Chronic glomerulonephritis	-	-	2	4.7
Inherited renal diseases	-	-	2	4.7
Idiopathic/unknown	25	14.45	9	21

Renal hypoplasia - dysplasia, urolithiasis, and PUV were the most common causes of CKD in this study and were found in 68 (39.3%), 47 (25.68%) and 33 cases (19.07%). Of the 186 cases of CAKUT (Fig. 1), 80 (43.01%), 54 (29.03%) and 24 (12.9%) cases most frequently reported hypoplasia, posterior urethral valve dysplasia and VUR.

Table 4: Comparison of Pattern of Renal diseases in current study with our previous study

Type of Study	Current Study	Previous Study ⁶	Percent Change
	One year March 2010-Feb 2011	10 years 1990-2000	
Study Period	602	2015	
Number of patients	602	2015	
Type of renal disease	N (%)	N (%)	
Primary Nephrotic Syndrome	297 (49.3)	863 (42.8)	↑06.50
Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)	173(28.7)	209(10.3)	↑18.40
Urinary Stone disease	24(4)	282(13.9)	↓09.90
Congenital Obstructive Uropathies	21(3.5)	127(6.30)	↓02.80
Acute Kidney Injury (AKI)	17(2.8)	28(1.38)	1.42
Acute Glomerulonephritis (AGN)	13(2.2)	58(2.84)	0.64
Hypoplastic kidneys	12(2)	44(2.18)	0.18
Urinary Tract Infection (UTI)	8(1.3)	146(7.24)	↓05.94
Secondary Glomerulonephritis (SGN)	8(1.3)	---	0.26
Neurogenic Bladder (NGB)	7(1.2)	19(0.94)	↓04.40
Primary Vesicoureteral Reflux (VUR)	5(0.8)	106(5.2)	↑
Congenital Nephrotic Syndrome	3(0.5)	---	1

Fig-1: Congenital anomalies of kidney and urinary tract (n 186).

DISCUSSION:

The paper highlights important aspects of the widespread epidemiology of kidney and urinary tract diseases in children and adolescents treated at the Institute during the research period. Recent results indicate that primary HF, CKD and urolithiasis are the most common primary kidney diseases in this region. Primary nephrotic syndrome is described as the most common renal dysfunction in children and adolescents worldwide. The reported frequency ranges from 18.5% to 60% in various surveys from different geographic regions. In African countries, its frequency ranges from 11% in South Africa to 40% in Egypt and Kenya. Research in Bangladesh and India also shows that PNS is the leading cause of admissions to the pediatric nephrology unit, but exact data are not available. The disease pattern in the current study differs slightly from our previously reported data (Table 4) and other studies from Pakistan and neighboring countries. The study found that the PNS frequency in the same center increased from 42.8% to 49% over 10 years, and this is in line with a recent Lahore study in which 51% of the 94 cases studied had PNS. However, in a previous Islamabad report, PNS was reported as the second most common kidney disorder after UTI and accounted for 20.5%. This variation in percentage can be attributed to the study type and inclusion criteria. In our previous study, we analyzed the data of all cases of children observed at the institute over a period of 10 years, while in the present study we included children visiting the hospital over a period of one year only. The GN pattern showed that primary PNS was the most common disorder, accounting for 92.5%, while secondary GN

accounted for 6.49%. It is also comparable to local and international literature. While the incidence of acute kidney injury (2.8%) in this study is not very high, it is nevertheless higher than in our previous report (1.4%) and lower than the last figure of 8.5% of hospital admissions. Acute kidney injury is a very severe disease seen in intensive care units (ICUs) with multiple organ failure and requires continuous renal replacement therapy or acute peritoneal dialysis, as shown by Jamal et al. The lower incidence may be due to the widespread use of oral rehydration therapy for dehydration that has been reported. The main cause of prerenal AKI, as well as the use of antibiotics to treat mycobacterial dysentery to avoid the hemolytic uremic syndrome associated with diarrhea, both are important causes of AKI in developing countries.² Urinary tract infections have been documented as the most common kidney problem in children, seen in tertiary centers in various reports, but not found in the present study (1.3%). This is much less than previously reported in Islamabad and Lahore, Pakistan. This can be explained by the fact that UTI is a frequent presentation of the underlying PUV, VUR, neurogenic bladder disease, and urolithiasis. Complicated UTIs may not have been the primary diagnosis. This low frequency in the present study may reflect isolated uncomplicated UTIs.

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights the current spectrum of kidney disease in children at the institute. Primary nephrotic syndrome, chronic kidney disease, and urinary stone disease were the most common kidney disorders in this study. Other important diseases include

congenital obstructive uropathy, hypoplastic dysplastic kidneys, acute kidney injury, and acute glomerulonephritis. Secondary GN, urinary tract infection, neurogenic bladder and primary VUR were observed least frequently. Compared to previously published data, the severity of all kidney and urinary diseases are increasing.

REFERENCES:

- Gimpel, Charlotte, E. Fred Avni, Luc Breyssem, Kathrin Burgmaier, Anna Caroli, Metin Cetiner, Dieter Haffner et al. "Imaging of kidney cysts and cystic kidney diseases in children: an International Working Group Consensus Statement." *Radiology* 290, no. 3 (2019): 769-782.
- Alwahaibi, Nasar Yousuf, Halima Khalfan Al Issaei, and Buthaina Saif Al Dhahli. "Incidence of pediatric glomerular diseases in Arab world: A systematic review." *Saudi Journal of Kidney Diseases and Transplantation* 30, no. 1 (2019): 15.
- Ibrahim, Halima Umar, Hassan Abdullahi Elechi, Adamu Ibrahim Rabasa, Garba Mohammed Ashir, Abubakar Garba Farouk, Mohammed Saad Yauba, and Bello Abdullahi Ibrahim. "Prevalence and pattern of human immunodeficiency virus-associated nephropathy among human immunodeficiency virus-positive children at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Nigeria." *Saudi Journal of Kidney Diseases and Transplantation* 30, no. 4 (2019): 843.
- Sheng, Nan, Jiali Ma, Wenwen Ding, and Ying Zhang. "Cluster analysis for family management of Chinese children with chronic kidney diseases." *Journal of health psychology* 25, no. 6 (2020): 755-765.
- Bonthuis, Marjolein, Jaap W. Groothoff, Gema Ariceta, Sergey Baikov, Nina Battelino, Anna Bjerre, Karlien Cransberg et al. "Growth Patterns After Kidney Transplantation in European Children Over the Past 25 Years: An ESPN/ERA-EDTA Registry Study." *Transplantation* 104, no. 1 (2020): 137-144.
- Mi, Sarah J., Nichole R. Kelly, Robert J. Brychta, Anne Claire Grammer, Manuela Jaramillo, Kong Y. Chen, Laura A. Fletcher et al. "Associations of sleep patterns with metabolic syndrome indices, body composition, and energy intake in children and adolescents." *Pediatric obesity* 14, no. 6 (2019): e12507.
- Fan, Jinjin, Kaifeng Xie, Liqin Wang, Nuoyan Zheng, and Xueqing Yu. "Roles of inflammasomes in inflammatory kidney diseases." *Mediators of inflammation* 2019 (2019).
- Hoffer, Fredric A., and John A. Kirkpatrick. "Radiology of interstitial lung disease in children." *Interstitial Lung Diseases in Children* 1 (2019): 73-99.
- Armstrong, Margaret E., and Christie P. Thomas. "Diagnosis of monogenic chronic kidney diseases." *Current opinion in nephrology and hypertension* 28, no. 2 (2019): 183-194.
- Thongboonkerd, Visith. "Roles for exosome in various kidney diseases and disorders." *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 10 (2019).
- Rebholz, Casey M., Bessie A. Young, Ronit Katz, Katherine L. Tucker, Teresa C. Carithers, Arnita F. Norwood, and Adolfo Correa. "Patterns of beverages consumed and risk of incident kidney disease." *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology* 14, no. 1 (2019): 49-56.
- Yildiz, Mehmet, Amra Adrovic, Emre Tasdemir, Khanim Baba-Zada, Muhammed Aydin, Oya Koker, Sezgin Sahin, Kenan Barut, and Ozgur Kasapcopur. "Evaluation of co-existing diseases in children with familial Mediterranean fever." *Rheumatology international* 40, no. 1 (2020): 57-64.
- Yin, Shi, Qinmu Peng, Hongming Li, Zhengqiang Zhang, Xinge You, Hangfan Liu, Katherine Fischer, Susan L. Furth, Gregory E. Tasian, and Yong Fan. "Multi-instance deep learning with graph convolutional neural networks for diagnosis of kidney diseases using ultrasound imaging." In *Uncertainty for Safe Utilization of Machine Learning in Medical Imaging and Clinical Image-Based Procedures*, pp. 146-154. Springer, Cham, 2019.
- Garrido, Deise, Andreia Watanabe, Ana Lúcia Ciamponi, Taciana Mara Couto, Levy Anderson César Alves, and Ana Estela Haddad. "Patterns of Internet and smartphone use by parents of children with chronic kidney disease." *PLoS one* 14, no. 2 (2019): e0212163.
- Wilson, Amy C., and Joseph T. Flynn. "Blood pressure in children with chronic kidney disease: lessons learned from the Chronic Kidney Disease in Children Cohort Study." *Pediatric Nephrology* (2019): 1-7.